

Hybrid-architecture finger mechanism towards dexterous and effective wearable hand exoskeletons

Chiara Brogi, Lorenzo Bartalucci, Nicola Secciani, Alessandro Ridolfi, Enrico Meli, and Benedetto Allotta
Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Florence, 50139 Florence, Italy
chiara.brogi@unifi.it - nicola.secciani@unifi.it

Abstract—Robotic assistance devices are becoming crucial tools for improving the life quality of people with disabilities. The hand is one of the most affected upper-limb parts, but fundamental for the subject’s interaction with the environment. Complete wearability, safety, compliance, comfort, lightness, small sizes, dexterity, sense-of-touch preservation, force effectiveness and affordability remain paramount for these devices’ success in everyday lives and activities. In this perspective, research trends focus on hybrid mechanical architectures that mix rigid and soft elements. This paper introduces a hybrid-architecture finger mechanism for wearable hand exoskeleton systems designed to meet as many of the requirements mentioned above as possible. An embodiment of the mechanism is presented and tested: as well as resulting suitable to be arranged in a five-finger hand exoskeleton, the new design shows remarkable performance, covering up to 85% of the finger range of motion and transmitting up to 16.78 N.

Index Terms—Wearable robotics, Hand exoskeletons, Finger mechanism, Hybrid architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization declares that over one billion people suffer from some form of disability, and numbers will soon increase due to different correlated factors. Increasing age, unhealthy eating habits, decreasing physical activity or visual acuity, and severe diseases such as diabetes, stroke, Parkinson’s, senile dementia, and tremor may negatively impact motor capabilities and even lead to complete limb dysfunction [1]. Besides, motor impairments are also expected at a younger age, e.g., due to traumas or congenital disorders [2]. Being the hand an extraordinarily sophisticated and dexterous tool that enables humans to interact with the surrounding environment with extreme flexibility, hand-function loss represents one of the most limiting disability. Current development trends are pushing research activities to investigate robotic assistance to physically replace lost hand functions when their recovery is no longer possible.

Last years’ literature is flooded with a wide variety of assistive Hand Exoskeleton Systems (HESs). Each device is developed with a specific target application and shows unique characteristics. However, in accordance with many reviews in the literature [3]–[6], it is possible to identify some ideal features that most exoskeletons are designed to possess:

- 1) *Complete wearability*: HESs shall be limited in dimensions and weight and fully standalone to preserve the wearer’s complete freedom of motion.

We acknowledge the support of the European Union by the Next Generation EU project ECS00000017 ‘Ecosistema dell’Innovazione’ Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE, PNRR, Spoke 9: Robotics and Automation for Health)

- 2) *Safety, compliance, and comfort*: HESs shall ensure the wearer’s safety and comfort over prolonged use. Compliant and customized devices are preferred; also, HESs shall always ensure a correct coupling with the hand to avoid wrong movements.
- 3) *Lightness and small size*: Assistive HESs are worn by impaired people over long periods and their use shall also be guaranteed in confined spaces. They shall not excessively exceed the limb dimensions and weigh more than 200 g on the hand and 500 g on the forearm.
- 4) *Dexterity*: HESs dexterity is correlated to the number of reproducible different gestures, which, in turn, depends on the number of independent finger mechanisms and total Degrees of Freedom (DOFs) of the system: broadly speaking, the more, the better.
- 5) *Sense-of-touch preservation*: Tactile sensations are crucial feedback for the human. The HESs shall not foreclose the touching of objects but preserve as much of the natural sense of touch as possible.
- 6) *Affordability*: As one of the Robotics for Medicine and Healthcare pillars, HESs (and robotic devices in general) shall democratize treatments and be affordable for all those in need.
- 7) *Force effectiveness*: Since assistive HESs primary purpose is to assist in everyday lives, they shall be able to exert suitable forces for typical everyday activities.

The literature offers many devices that do not present all such features. This is because fulfilling these requirements does not always lead in one direction, but usually on discordant ones that require trade-offs.

A. Paper contribution

The main contribution of this paper is to present a hybrid-architecture mechanism for driving the flexion/extension (f/e) movement of the finger. It is designed as the base concept module to be embedded in an original assistive HES (Figure 1) aiming to show the crucial characteristics mentioned above while minimizing trade-offs. In particular, the focus of this work is on the use of a specific mechanical architecture that simultaneously takes advantage of rigid structures features (i.e., kinematic accuracy, high force transmission, parametrization, optimization, and customization of geometries) and soft ones (i.e., lightness, reduced dimensions, compliance). Besides, the mechanism actuation system is thought to act independently on the corresponding finger. Its shape and dimension are carefully

Fig. 1. The newest exoskeleton prototype designed by the Mechatronics and Dynamic Modelling Lab at the University of Florence.

designed to be arranged in a five-finger HES configuration, meaning that each finger can be moved individually from the others. In the background is the emphasis on developing a fully wearable standalone device.

II. METHODS

A. Hybrid-architecture design

The complexity of finger-mechanism rigid architectures drastically increases as the number of anatomical joints actuated grows (especially if distal), as in [7], [8]. Intending to keep the size of the mechanism small while still ensuring the actuation of all the finger f/e joints, the proposed design acts on the MetaCarpophalangeal (MCP) joint through a rigid kinematic chain and on the others — the Proximal Interphalangeal (PIP, or IP in the case of the thumb) and the Distal Interphalangeal (DIP) for the “long fingers” — through a soft architecture involving flat springs. A passive DOF was added for the ab/adduction motion of the MCP joint, thus improving the device’s dexterity and compliance.

Regarding force effectiveness, the rigid kinematic chain was designed to exert at least 15 N on the middle of the proximal phalanx through Link 3 (Figure 2). A four-bar mechanism was selected for this purpose as it was used to identify a Remote Center of Motion (RCM) for the first phalanx right in the proximity of the natural MCP joint. The force target was instead chosen according to literature [9] as suitable for daily object manipulation. An internally developed and already validated numerical procedure [10] was adapted to the case study to kinematically optimize the link dimensions on the user’s anatomy. Once the geometry of the rigid architecture was customized, a kinetostatic analysis was performed to calculate the torque the mechanism has to guarantee so that Link 3 exerts at least the target force on the finger. The *Principle of Virtual Works* was exploited to conduct the analysis, and the results showed a maximum of 238.86 Nmm required.

The soft architecture actuates the f/e motion of the distal and, in the case of “long finger”, of the intermediate phalanges. This choice has been made to keep the mechanism’s vertical

Fig. 2. The proposed hybrid-architecture finger mechanism.

clearance over the finger as limited as possible to boost the fine manipulation capabilities of the device. A flat spring was chosen for this purpose, producing the f/e movement through the relative rotation between Link 2 and 3. Geometric considerations in designing spring housings enable determining another RCM in the desired spot.

B. Mechanism embodiment

Taking into account the target torque, a 6V-low power Pololu Micro Metal Gearmotor (380:1) was chosen as the mechanism actuator. Considering the strict transversal clearance requirement to house five finger mechanisms on the hand back, a coupling of steel (C45) and brass bevel gears by KG Gears was used as driving and driven wheels. This 1:2 gear ratio, coupled with the Micro Metal Gearmotor, allows for a transmissible torque that, at stall condition, reaches the value of 568.98 Nmm, which is high enough to exert the target torque and prevent overheating issues. The driven shaft (AISI 316) was designed to house the cylindrical pin allowing for the passive ab/adduction DOF, and according to the expected loads under the motor stall condition.

As regards the soft architecture, instead, a rectangular-shaped flat spring in spring steel was exploited. Two holes were drilled at its ends, enabling connections to Link 2 and the distal phalanx end-effector.

Finally, a linear-voltage magnetic rotary encoder from RLS (RM08VB0010B02L2G00 - RMM3010A1A00) was added (Figure 2) to provide a direct measure of the finger f/e angle.

III. TEST AND RESULTS

A finger mechanism prototype was first tailor-made and 3D printed for the thumb of a healthy subject enrolled in performing preliminary evaluations of the achievable ROM and exerted forces upon signing an informed consent.

Some motion tests were performed with the finger module worn by the subject to evaluate if the hybrid architecture could follow the finger f/e movement while covering its ROM as much as possible. The complete f/e movement was repeated 10 times while the scene was filmed. The images were elaborated through the open software Kinovea, measuring the maximum f/e angles of the MCP and IP joints. The same values were

Fig. 3. The component designed for housing the FSR during its characterization and force measurement, on the top. On the bottom, the experimental configuration is shown.

also monitored through the encoder (hooked up to an Arduino Nano Every board), and the measurements validated the data from Kinovea. The same task was performed with and without the finger mechanism for comparison. As a result, the MCP joint ROM was covered entirely, while coverage of roughly 85% of the IP joint ROM was reached.

The exerted forces were measured using an FSR 406 force-sensing resistor. The setup for force measurements, including a custom 3D-printed housing for the FSR, is shown in Figure 3. Before the test, the FSR was characterized using known weights to derive the actual force measured based on the recorded output voltage. After the characterization, the finger module was worn by the subject, who was asked to remain as passive as possible while the actuation system drove the mechanism to push against the 3D-printed FSR support. A commercial Myo Armband sensor by Thalmic Labs was exploited to monitor the myoelectric activity of the subject's forearm during the test to ensure that the muscular contribution was neglectable. The actuator power supply was limited to 90% of the stall current to avoid excessive overheating. Twenty seconds after reaching the motion stall (once the transitory phase of the system was ended), ten measures at 1-Hz frequency were acquired, and their average was calculated. The process was repeated seven times, and the results, visible in Table I, show that the target force was rather achieved with a mean value of about 10.6 N and a maximum of 16.78 N.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The developed finger module is 23 mm wide, 28 mm high and 72.5 mm long, weighing less than 60 g. Achievements in terms of overall dimensions, weight, force effectiveness, and covered ROM led to designing the assistive HES in Figure 1

TABLE I
THE AVERAGE VALUES FOR THE FORCE MEASUREMENTS, IN TERMS OF 10-BIT FSR READING, CORRESPONDING VOLTAGE, AND FORCE.

	FSR reading	Voltage [V]	Force [N]
Measurement 1	810	3,96	5,94
Measurement 2	847	4,14	7,81
Measurement 3	917	4,48	16,78
Measurement 4	887	4,33	11,31
Measurement 5	898	4,39	12,79
Measurement 6	890	4,35	11,66
Measurement 7	848	4,15	7,89

by repeating the same module after tailoring the finger mechanisms to the different finger dimensions. Thus, as well as *small sizes* and *force effectiveness* requirements met, *dexterity* was pursued by enabling independent finger movement, while the optimization procedure ensures *compliance and comfort*. The whole HES reached about 300 g on the hand back, which is, instead, still above the requirements of *lightness*. The electronic components and power supply system are thought to be placed in a box fixed to the forearm, enabling the device's *complete wearability*. The *sense of touch* is preserved by exploiting just the back of the hand and thanks to Velcro straps for connecting the HES to the hand. Last but not least, it is worth noting that the cost of the whole HES is estimated to be around 1500 €, including the 3D printed and commercial components, thus guaranteeing its *affordability*.

The new finger mechanism as a whole promises remarkable performance. The resulting HES will soon be tested in a proper environment to verify that these promises are indeed fulfilled.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. A. İncel, "Functional Assessment in Geriatric Hand," *Hand Function*, Springer, pp. 211–225, 2019.
- [2] M. den Hollander, A. Hoekstra, "Hand Function in Children with Congenital Disorders," *Hand Function*, Springer, pp. 189–200, 2019.
- [3] T. du Plessis, K. Djouani, C. Oosthuizen, "A review of active hand exoskeletons for rehabilitation and assistance," *Robotics*, vol. 10, 2021.
- [4] M. Sarac, M. Solazzi, A. Frisoli, "Design Requirements of Generic Hand Exoskeletons and Survey of Hand Exoskeletons for Rehabilitation, Assistive, or Haptic Use," *IEEE Transactions on Haptics*, vol. 12, n. 4, pp. 400–413, 2019.
- [5] C. Y. Chu, R. M. Patterson, "Soft robotic devices for hand rehabilitation and assistance: a narrative review," *Journal of neuroengineering and rehabilitation*, vol. 15, n. 1, 2018.
- [6] T. Desplenter, Y. Zhou, B. Edmonds, M. Lidka, A. Goldman, A. L. Trejos, "Rehabilitative and assistive wearable mechatronic upper-limb devices: A review," *Journal of Rehabilitation and Assistive Technologies Engineering*, vol. 7, 2020.
- [7] D. Esposito, J. Centracchio, E. Andreozzi, S. Savino, G. D. Gargiulo, G. R. Naik, and P. Bifulco, "Design of a 3D-Printed Hand Exoskeleton Based on Force-Myography Control for Assistance and Rehabilitation," *Machines*, vol. 10, n. 1, 2022.
- [8] Y. Yun, S. Dancausse, P. Esmatloo, A. Serrato, C. A. Merring, P. Agarwal, A. D. Deshpande, "Maestro: An EMG-driven assistive hand exoskeleton for spinal cord injury patients," 2017 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation (ICRA), pp. 2904–2910, 2017.
- [9] K. Matheus, A. M. Dollar, "Benchmarking grasping and manipulation: Properties of the objects of daily living," 2010 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems, pp. 5020–5027, 2010.
- [10] M. Bianchi, F. Fanelli, E. Meli, A. Ridolfi, F. Vannetti, M. Bianchini, B. Allotta, "Optimization-based scaling procedure for the design of fully portable hand exoskeletons," *Meccanica*, vol. 53, n. 11-12, pp. 3157–3175, 2018.